

Supplemental Table 9. Data charting for all studies assessing the association between education and GWG.

Author	Year	Country	Study design	Source of GWG data; guideline used	Study population	Sample size	Significant findings	Non-significant findings	Education categories	Study sample primarily included individuals with a vulnerability factor?	Findings
Alhusen, J. L.	2017	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Women who gave birth from 2004-11 and completed the Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System survey	251 342	Odds of excessive GWG decreased if low education (<12 yrs vs 12+ years); odds of insufficient GWG increased if low education		< High school ≥ High school	No	S
Beydoun, H. A.	2011	USA	Retrospective	Self-reported; IOM 1990	Respondents of the 2000-06 Oklahoma Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System who were ≥20 years of age	11 561	Higher education was a protective factor against insufficient GWG; higher odds of excessive GWG if higher education (>12 yrs vs <12 yrs)	NS association with odds of excessive GWG if education vs <12 yrs education	< High school High school > High school	No	S & NS
Bjermo, H.	2015	Sweden	Retrospective	Medical records; IOM 2009	Women included in the Swedish Medical Birth Register from 1992-2010	378 529	Higher risk of excessive GWG in normal weight women with low education (high school or less) vs. high education (university education or doctoral degree); in overweight/obese women: slightly lower risk of excessive GWG if low education (vs. high education; adjusted RR)		≤ High school University	No	S
Bogaerts, A.	2012	Belgium	Prospective	Medical records; IOM 2009	Women who delivered in Flanders in 2009	54 022	Women with university degrees had lower odds for excessive and insufficient GWG (vs. women with a full high school education); higher odds of insufficient GWG in women with only a primary level education (vs. full high school education)	NS effect of primary school education or some high school education (as compared to full high school education) on excessive GWG; no effect of some high school education (as compared to full high school education) on odds of insufficient GWG	Primary school (very low) Lower grade high school (low) High school (medium) Bachelor degree (high) Masters/doctorate degree (highest)	No	S & NS
Caulfield, L. E.	1996	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 1990	Black and White women who delivered at John Hopkins Department of Gynecology and Obstetrics from 1987-89	3 870	Lower risk of insufficient GWG if higher education (>12 years vs 12 years)	NS effect of higher education (>12 years vs 12 years) on excessive GWG; NS effect of low education (<12 years as compared to 12 years) on insufficient or excessive GWG	< High school High school > High school	No	S & NS
Chagarlamud i, H.	2018	USA	Retrospective	Medical records; IOM 2009	Women attending an outpatient obstetrics/gynecology clinic that mainly serves a low-income community (2012-13) in North Carolina	410		NS difference in education levels (≤ grade 11, high school graduate/GED, some college/vocational school, or college graduate or higher) between women who had insufficient, adequate, or excessive GWG	≤ Grade 11 High school/GED Some college/vocational-technical school College graduate or higher	Yes	NS
Chasan-Taber, L.	2008	USA	Prospective	Medical records; IOM 1990	Hispanic (primarily Puerto Rican), low-income women receiving prenatal care at a public clinic from 2000-03	770		Education (< high school, high school/trade/technical school, college) not significantly associated with GWG	< High school High school/trade/technical school College	Yes	NS
Chasan-Taber, L.	2014	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Hispanic women (Puerto Rican or Dominican Republic heritage) seeking prenatal care at a public clinic from 2006-11	1 276	Significant difference in GWG adequacy (insufficient, adequate, or excessive) according to level of education (categories: < high school, high school or GED, some college/graduate)		< High school High school or GED Some college/college graduate	Yes	S
Chasan-Taber, L.	2016	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Hispanic women (Puerto Rican or Dominican Republic heritage) seeking prenatal care at a public clinic from 2006-11	1 293	Significant difference in GWG adequacy (insufficient, adequate, or excessive) according to level of education (categories: < high school, high school graduate, some college/graduate)		< High school High school Some college/college graduate	Yes	S
Cheng, H. R.	2015	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	White non-Hispanic and Asian non-Hispanic (Asian Indian, Chinese, Filipino, Japanese, Korean, or Vietnamese) women who were documented in the 2009 Texas birth certificate data	114 632	Higher risk of excessive GWG if some college education (as compared to high school or less)	NS difference in risk of excessive GWG if higher educated (university degree vs high school or less); NS difference in risk of insufficient GWG according to level of education	≤ High school Some college Bachelor degree Graduate degree	No	S & NS

Chihara, I.	2014	USA	Retrospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Low income women who were enrolled in Hawaii's Special Supplemental Nutrition Program for Women, Infants, and Children from 2003-05	19 130	Significant difference in GWG adequacy based on education (< 12 years, 12 years/high school, >12 years)	< High school High school > High school	Yes	S	
Cohen, A. K.	2016	USA	Retrospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Participants of the 1979 National Longitudinal Survey of Youth who were 14-22 years old in 1979	2 769	Women with <u>normal prepregnancy weight</u> with less education had higher odds of excessive GWG (as compared to adequate GWG; education categories: not graduated from high school and graduated from high school vs. college students); less education protected against excessive GWG <u>among Black women</u> (less than a high school degree vs high school degree); <u>White women</u> with less than a high school degree were more likely to have excessive GWG than those who graduated high school and those with a college degree; less education increased odds of insufficient GWG (less than high school vs college & high school vs college)	NS difference in odds of insufficient GWG if less than high school degree, as compared to high school degree; NS interaction by race/ethnicity on odds of insufficient GWG by educational attainment; NS effect of education on excessive GWG in Hispanic or overweight women; NS difference in odds of excessive GWG if high school degree vs college degree for all race/ethnicities; NS effect of less than high school vs high school on odds of excessive GWG between normal weight and overweight women	< High school High school College	No	S & NS
Deputy, N. P.	2015	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Participants of the 2010-11 Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System	44 421	<u>Underweight</u> : higher odds of insufficient and excessive GWG with education less than high school (compared to high school) <u>Normal weight</u> : higher odds of insufficient GWG if lower education (<12 yrs vs 12 yrs) <u>Overweight</u> : higher odds of excessive GWG if education more than high school (vs high school) <u>Obese</u> : none	Education: NS effect of higher education (>12 yrs vs 12 years) on GWG adequacy (except in overweight - higher risk of excessive GWG)	< High school High school > High school	No	S & NS
Djakovic, I.	2019	Croatia	Cross-sectional	Self-reported; no GWG guideline identified	Women in their second pregnancy at a single site university hospital	113	Higher total GWG in low education (high school educated vs college/university)	High school University	No	S	
Gaillard, R.	2013	Netherlands	Prospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Multi-site study with pregnant women in Rotterdam from 2001-05	6 959		NS effect of education (primary or secondary vs higher education) on odds of excessive GWG	< High school High school > High school	No	NS
Guillot, N.	2015	USA (Puerto Rico)	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Multi-site study with pregnant women in northern Puerto Rico from 2011-14	160		NS associations were observed between GWG adequacy and education (high school education or less vs more than high school)	≤ High school > High school	Yes	NS
Haile, Z. T.	2017	USA	Retrospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Participants of the population-based Infant Feeding Practices Study II from 2005-07	2 053	Significant differences in GWG adequacy by education (high school or less, some college, college graduate)	≤ High school Some college College	No	S	
Headen, I.	2018	USA	Prospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Participants of the 1979 National Longitudinal Survey of Youth who were 14-21 years old in 1979	3 300	Significant differences in GWG adequacy according to level of education (<12 yrs, 12-15 yrs, 16+ yrs)	< High school High school or some postsecondary (12-15 yrs) Postsecondary (16+ yrs)	No	S	
Herring, S. J.	2012	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Urban, low-income, primarily Black women seeking prenatal care at a university hospital from 2009-11	94		NS association between excessive GWG and education (high school or less vs some college or more)	≤ High school Some college or more	Yes	NS
Hickey, C. A.	1997a	USA	Prospective	Measured; IOM 1990	Low-income Black and White women with one or more risk factors for fetal growth restriction, who enrolled in prenatal care at specific university-operated clinics from 1985-88	806		NS association between insufficient GWG and education	<8 yrs 8-12 yrs ≥12 yrs	Yes	NS

Hickey, C. A.	1992b	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; GWG evaluated as a percent of standard W/H (Rosso, 1985)	Low-income, Black and Hispanic women enrolled in prenatal care at two university-operated clinics	150	Women who had higher education were at increased risk of low GWG (in univariate analysis: education was only significant for Hispanic women)	Continuous variable (number of years)	Yes	S	
Holowko, N.	2014	Sweden	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Primiparous women who gave birth from 1982-2008 and were in the third generation of the Uppsala Birth Cohort Study	4 080	Lower education increased odds of excessive GWG (vs adequate GWG) in normal weight women (elementary or secondary education vs tertiary education)	NS effect of education on GWG adequacy (excessive or insufficient GWG) for overweight/obese women; effect on underweight women could not be analysed with OR due to low statistical power (but NS difference in proportion of underweight women with insufficient/adequate/excessive GWG)	< High school High school > High school (tertiary education)	No	S & NS
Holowko, N.	2015	Sweden	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Women with 2 pregnancies included in the Swedish Medical Birth Register and the Education Register from 1982-2010	163 352	Differing effects of education on adequacy of GWG (insufficient or excessive vs adequate) based on BMI and parity; in general: lower education was associated with higher odds of excessive GWG in underweight (1st pregnancy only) and normal weight women (1st and 2nd pregnancy); intermediate education reduced odds of insufficient GWG for underweight and normal weight women in 1st pregnancy; higher odds of insufficient GWG in overweight women with low/intermediate education (for 2nd pregnancy; 1st pregnancy: only associated with low education)	NS effect of education on GWG adequacy (odds of excessive or insufficient GWG, as compared to adequate) for obese women during pregnancy 1 or 2	≤ High school (≤10 years; low) Some high school/high school (≤13 years; intermediate) Postsecondary (high)	No	S & NS
Howie, L. D.	2003	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 1990	Women included in the 2000 US Natality File (excluding women from California, as GWG there is not collected)	2 796 805	Lower odds of excessive GWG if lower education (less than high school for women 18 yrs or older, or if education was 6 or fewer years less than woman's age when <18 yrs old)	< High school (adjusted if woman was <18 yrs old) ≥ High school	No	S	
Huynh, M.	2014	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Primiparous women who gave birth from 1999-2001 in New York City, were ≥20 years old, and either White non-Hispanic, Black non-Hispanic, or Hispanic	56 911	High school or some college increased risk of excessive GWG (compared to those with less than a high school education); lower odds of excessive GWG if White non-Hispanic with college or more education; Hispanic women with high school or more education had higher risk of excessive GWG than those with less than high school education; women with at least high school education who are living in low or medium SES neighborhood have an increased risk of excessive GWG (compared to less than high school education); significant difference in prevalence of excessive GWG in women who use Medicaid when analyzed according to level of education (no sub-group analysis)	NS difference in prevalence of excessive GWG between highest and lowest levels of education (college or more vs less than high school education) when not divided by race/ethnicity and neighborhood SES; prevalence of excessive GWG did not vary by education level in Black non-Hispanic women, while White non-Hispanic women did not have a significant difference between high school education or some college when compared to less than high school education; NS difference in prevalence of excessive GWG according to level of education for those living in a high SES neighbourhood	< High school High school/GED Some college (13-15 yrs) College or more (≥16 yrs)	No	S & NS
Johnson, P. J.	2002	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 1990	Primarily low-income, urban women seeking prenatal care at a specific clinic from 1997-98	578	<u>Distribution of women in GWG adequacy categories (insufficient, adequate, excessive):</u> significant difference by education (looked at inadequate education, i.e. not having completed the expected number of years of schooling; only significant for adolescents)	<u>Distribution of women in GWG adequacy categories:</u> for adults only: NS association with inadequate education	< High school (adjusted if woman was <18 yrs old) ≥ High school	Yes	S & NS
Khanolkar, A. R.	2017	USA	Retrospective	Medical record/birth certificate; IOM 2009	All women who gave birth in Washington State from 2006-08	181 948	Significant difference in adequacy of GWG according to education level (12th grade or less, high school graduate, some college, associates degree, bachelor's degree, postgraduate degree)	≤ High school High school Some college Associate degree Bachelor's degree Postgraduate degree	No	S	

Kinnunen, T. I.	2016	Norway	Prospective	Measured; IOM 2009	Multi-site study with pregnant women seeking prenatal care in Eastern Oslo from 2008-10	632	Negative relationship between GWG and education (<10 years vs university or college)	NS difference in total GWG between 10-12 yrs of education vs university/college education	<10 yrs 10-12 yrs University or college	No	S & NS
Kowal, C.	2012	Canada	Retrospective	Self-reported; Health Canada 2010 (IOM 2009)	Respondents of the Canadian Maternity Experiences Survey of 2006, all of whom were ≥15 years old	6,233 (weighted to n=74,523)	Higher odds of excessive GWG (vs adequate GWG) if less than a high school education (compared to university graduate)	NS difference in odds of excessive GWG if high school education or post secondary diploma (as compared to university graduate); NS difference in odds of insufficient GWG according to education level	< High school High school Post-secondary diploma University	No	S & NS
Krukowski, R. A.	2013	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Black and White respondents of the Arkansas Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System from 2004-08 who had adequate or excessive GWG	4 619		NS difference in women with adequate vs excessive GWG according to level of education (high school degree or less)	High school or less	No	NS
Larranaga, I.	2013	Spain	Prospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Multi-site study with pregnant women seeking prenatal care from 2004-08	2 607		NS difference between level of education (university vs primary or secondary education) and GWG outside of recommendations (compared adequate GWG to combined insufficient/excessive GWG)	< High school High school > High school (university education)	No	NS
Lowell, H.	2010	Canada	Retrospective	Self-reported; Health Canada 1999 IOM 1990)	Respondents of the 2006 national Maternity Experiences Survey, all of whom were ≥15 years old	5 554	Significantly higher prevalence of excessive GWG with less than secondary education	NS difference in prevalence of insufficient GWG according to education (less than secondary, secondary, some postsecondary/diploma/certificate, university degree)	< High school High school Some postsecondary/diploma/certificate University	No	S & NS
Margerison-Zilko, C.	2014	USA	Prospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Participants of the 1979 National Longitudinal Survey of Youth, all of whom were 14-22 years of age in 1979	5 175	Effect of extreme unexpected economic contraction differed by education: lower risk of excessive GWG if higher education (greater than high school as compared to high school)	NS difference in risk of insufficient GWG by education and NS difference in risk of excessive GWG if lower education (less than high school vs high school)	< High school High school > High school	No	S & NS
Mehta, U.	2011	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 1990	Participants of the PIN study (Pregnancy, Infection and Nutrition study) who attended prenatal care at University of North Carolina hospitals from January 2001 - June 2005; all women were > 16 years	1 192	Education: women with <16 years of education preferring a light body were at higher risk of excessive GWG (compared to those preferring an average size)	NS difference in risk of excessive GWG if high education (16+ years) and have a light vs average body size preference	<12 yrs 12-<16 yrs ≥16 yrs	No	S & NS
Meng, Y.	2018	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Black women seeking prenatal care at one of two clinics from 2008-11, all of whom were ≥18 years of age and enrolled in Medicaid and/or the Special Supplemental Nutrition Program for Women, Infants, and Children	55	Higher GWG associated with lower education (measured by grades of education)		Continuous variable (number of years)	Yes	S
Nunnery, D.	2018	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Women attending a WIC clinic in (for low-income women) in 2014 who were receiving WIC as a maternity client and were ≥18 years old	160		In multivariate regression: NS association between education (high school or less vs more than high school) and odds of excessive GWG	≤ High school > High school	Yes	NS

Park, J. H.	2011	Korea	Retrospective	Medical records; no GWG guideline identified (no official guidelines in Korea)	Single-site study of women who gave birth at a university hospital from 2005-07	2 311	Insufficient GWG (<10 kg) significantly more prevalent in women with lower education (12 yrs or less)	≤ High school	No	S	
Pawlak, M.	2015	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Women who gave birth in Colorado from 2007-10	230 698	Decreased odds of insufficient GWG if higher education (high school, some college, college or higher as compared to having some high school); decreased odds of excessive GWG if highest education (college or more vs some high school), single/separated (vs married/living with partner)	NS effect on excessive GWG if high school graduate or have some college (as compared to some high school)	Some high school High school Some college College or more	No	S & NS
Platner, M. H.	2019	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Women who gave birth in New York City from 2008-2012	515 148	Significant differences in adequacy of GWG based on education (<high school, high school, some college, college graduate or higher)	< High school High school Some college College or more	No	S	
Sangi-Haghpeykar, H.	2014	USA	Cross-sectional	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Hispanic women who delivered at a specific hospital in Texas	282		NS difference in adequacy of GWG according to education (in years)	Continuous variable (number of years)	Yes	NS
Siega-Riz, A. M.	1997	USA	Prospective	Measured; IOM 1990	Hispanic, primarily low-income women attending public prenatal clinics and who participated in a prematurity prevention project	6 114	Multivariate linear regression model for <u>total GWG</u> : positive association with education	NS effect on odds of <u>insufficient GWG</u> (for all women): education (<8 yrs or >12 yrs)	< 8 yrs > 12 yrs	Yes	S & NS
Walker, L. O.	2014	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Hispanic and White non-Hispanic women who gave birth in 2009 in Texas and were ≥18 years old	250 857	Increased odds of insufficient GWG (vs adequate GWG) if less than high school education (vs high school or more); increased odds of excessive GWG if lower education (less than high school vs high school or more)	< High school ≥ High school	No	S	
Walker, L. O.	2009	USA	Retrospective	Self-reported; IOM 1990	Hispanic women who responded to the New Mexico Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System from 2000-03, all of whom were ≥18 years old	1 988	Significant differences in general GWG adequacy according to education (0-8 yrs, 9-11, 12, 13-15, ≥16 yrs)	NS association between odds of insufficient GWG and education level (0-8, 9-11, 12, 13-15, 16+ yrs)	0-8 yrs 9-11 yrs High school (12 yrs) 13-15 yrs ≥16 yrs	Yes	S & NS
Wells, C. S.	2006	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 1990	Respondents of the 2000-02 Colorado Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System	4 528	Higher odds of insufficient GWG if <12 years or 12 yrs of education (as compared to >12 years); higher odds of excessive GWG if completed 12 years of education (vs >12 yrs)	NS effect on excessive GWG risk if <12 years of education (as compared to >12 years)	< High school High school > High school	No	S & NS